

Maßnahmen gegen Pseudowissenschaft.

Infolge Auflösung der Bundesrepublik Deutschland und weiterer Maßnahmen zur [Entnazifizierung von Deutschland](#), ist jegliche Förderung verbotener Organisationen und ihrer Tätigkeit sowie Beteiligung an solchen Organisationen und Tätigkeiten unerlaubt und muß unaufgefordert unterlassen werden, um strafrechtliche Konsequenzen zu vermeiden. Weil die deutsche Pseudowissenschaft selbst die Vorstellung davon verfälschte, was erlaubt und unerlaubt, rechtens und rechtswidrig, richtig und falsch ist, muß die deutsche Pseudowissenschaft und die von den deutschen Nazitäter betriebene pseudowissenschaftliche Propaganda effektiv behoben werden. Um das zu gewährleisten, ordne ich die Schließung aller Einrichtungen und Institutionen an, welche die Pseudowissenschaft betreiben und die Wissenschaft verfälschen, einschließlich [Springer Nature](#), [Holtzbrinck Publishing](#), [BC Partners](#), [Internationale Mathematische Union](#), [Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur](#), [Leibniz Institut für Psychologie](#), [Leibniz Gemeinschaft](#), zusätzlich zur [Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft](#) und zum [Internationalen Wissenschaftsrat](#). Das gesamte Vermögen dieser Organisationen übertrage ich der Stiftung für die Errichtung der konstitutionellen Ordnung.

Dr. Andrej Poleev
Berlin, 24.11.2024

Measures against pseudoscience.

Following the annulment and prohibition of the Federal Republic of Germany and further measures aimed to [denazify Germany](#), any promotion of prohibited organizations and their activities as well as participation in such organizations and activities is unlawful and must be discontinued without further demand in order to avoid any consequences under criminal law. Because German pseudoscience itself has distorted the notion of what is permissible and impermissible, legal and illegal, right and wrong, German pseudoscience and the pseudoscientific propaganda practiced by German Nazi criminals must be effectively eliminated. To ensure this, I order the closure of all bodies and institutions that promote pseudoscience and falsify science, including [Springer Nature](#), [Holtzbrinck Publishing](#), [BC Partners](#), [International Mathematical Union](#), [Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure](#), [Leibniz Institute for Psychology](#), [Leibniz Association](#), in addition to the [German Research Foundation](#) and the [International Science Council](#). I transfer all the assets and property of these organizations to the Foundation for Constitutional Development.

Dr. Andrej Poleev
Berlin, 24.11.2024

„Public health officials must work to regain American's trust, Americans want to be educated, not indoctrinated.“ — Brad Wenstrup, Chairman of the Select Subcommittee on the Coronavirus Pandemic. In: *After Action Review of the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Lessons Learned and a Path Forward. Final Report of the Select Subcommittee on the Coronavirus Pandemic, Committee on Oversight and Accountability of the U.S. House of Representatives, 2024.*

„The ignoring of scientific psychology, which was eroded by various pseudoscientific concepts, led subsequently to a rampant democracy in which any distinction between mental health and disease was lost, and this in turn led to the overpowering of psychopaths that continues to this day. Psychopaths have turned schools, whether schools of general education, universities, or such of specialized higher education, into factories for the production of psychopaths, just as defective prion proteins cause a chain reaction of conformational transformation of normal proteins homologous to them into pathogenic ones. The unlearned lesson in the history of psychology is that there is still no scientifically sound certification system for psychologists, and the consequence is the inability to counter psychopaths and psychopathological tendencies in society. That is why the reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association and the reexamination of psychologists based on criteria of scientificity and rightfulness is necessary to put an end to arbitrariness and irresponsibility.“ — A. Poleev. [Professional aptitude in psychology](#). In: [Letters to the American People, Part II \(2019 – 2024\)](#). Enzymes, 2024.

Springer is a publisher of academic literature and, measured by the number of publications and citations as well as its commercial efficiency, is one of the leading and most successful companies in academic publishing. A closer look behind the facade of his seemingly success story, which began in Berlin in 1842, reveals a very different picture. After answering the questions: What Springer really is? and: Why has it so far escaped the sanctions imposed on other German corporations such as Volkswagen and Bayer?, the author explains why it is necessary to re-establish the International Psychoanalytical Association.

A. Poleev. Springer. In: [Metaanalysis of psychoanalysis](#). Enzymes, 2019.

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„Errors are the greatest obstacles to the progress of science; to correct such errors is of more practical value than to achieve new knowledge,“ asserted Eugen Bleuler in his monograph on Schizophrenia. Basic error of several prevailing classification schemes of pathological conditions, as for example ICD-10, lies in confusing and mixing symptoms with diseases, what makes them unscientific. Considering the need to bring order into the chaos and light into terminological obscureness, I introduce the Causal classification of diseases originating from the notion of bodily wholeness and causality of its loss.

A. Poleev. [Causal classification of diseases](#). Enzymes, 2020.

λογισμὸς δὲ βραχὺ μὲν ὄνομα, τελειότατον δὲ καὶ θειότατον ἔργον, τῆς τοῦ παντὸς ψυχῆς ἀπόσπασμα ἢ, ὅπερ ὀσιώτερον εἶπεῖν τοῖς κατὰ Μωυσῆν φιλοσοφοῦσιν, εἰκόνας θείας ἐκμαγεῖον ἐμφερές. Φίλων ο Αλεξανδρεὺς. Περί των μετονομαζομένων και ων ἔνεκα μετονομάζονται.

A. Poleev. Knowledge and stupidity. In: [The sense of life and other psychological essays](#). Enzymes, 2024.

A. Poleev. [Science in 21st century](#). Enzymes, 2024.

[The Return of Pseudosciences in Artificial Intelligence: Have Machine Learning and Deep Learning Forgotten Lessons from Statistics and History?](#)

[Problems in AI, their roots in philosophy, and implications for science and society.](#)